

Appendix to article "Source Code Refactoring Based on LLM and UML Extension"

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A Formal Definitions and Metrics

A.1 Formal Definition of Refactoring

Refactoring is a change to the internal structure of a program without changing its external behavior. A formal definition of refactoring is

$$R = (pre, T, post), \quad (1)$$

where pre denotes the preconditions for applying the refactoring, T is the program transformation, and $post$ denotes the postconditions after refactoring.

In this paper, the main role of preconditions is to determine whether a specific refactoring is applicable in a given situation and thereby to prevent undesired changes to the system's external behavior. In the proposed approach, this applicability is determined primarily by anxiety functions.

A.2 Anxiety Functions for Defective Code Regions

God class

$$Anx_1 = 0.6 \cdot \frac{CS}{CSR} + 0.4 \cdot \frac{WMC}{WMC R}. \quad (2)$$

Here CS is class size and

$$WMC = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i, \quad w_i = E - N + 2P, \quad (3)$$

where n is the number of methods in the class, E is the number of edges in the control-flow graph, N is the number of vertices, and P is the number of connected components.

Refactoring approach: split the class into several smaller classes or extract subclasses.

A class with divergent modifications

$$Anx_2 = 0.4 \cdot \frac{CBO}{CBOR} + 0.3 \cdot \frac{RFC}{RFCR} + 0.3 \cdot \frac{COF}{COFR}. \quad (4)$$

Coupling between objects is defined as

$$CBO(C) = |\{D \in Classes \mid D \neq C \wedge (C \text{ uses } D \vee D \text{ uses } C)\}|. \quad (5)$$

Refactoring approach: reduce coupling and extract a dedicated class.

Fragmented class The formula and refactoring approach are analogous to Divergent Change.

Class with parallel inheritance hierarchies

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Anx}_3 &= 0.5 \cdot \text{inheri}(\text{DIT}_1, \text{DIT}_2, \text{NOC}_1, \text{NOC}_2) \\ &+ 0.5 \cdot \frac{\text{CBO/CBOR} + \text{RFC/RFCR} + \text{COF/COFR}}{3}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\text{inheri}(\text{DIT}_1, \text{DIT}_2, \text{NOC}_1, \text{NOC}_2) = \begin{cases} 2, & \text{if the hierarchies are structurally similar,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Here DIT is the depth of the inheritance tree and NOC is the number of subclasses. Structural similarity means that the compared hierarchies have closely matching values of DIT and NOC.

Refactoring approach: move methods or fields to other classes, split a large class, or merge hierarchies.

Lazy class

$$\text{Anx}_4 = 0.5 \cdot \text{lazy}(\text{DIT}) + 0.3 \cdot \text{blank}(\text{CS}, \text{NOF}) + 0.2 \cdot \text{RFC}, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{lazy}(\text{DIT}) &= \begin{cases} 2, & \text{DIT} \in \{1\} \cup [19, \infty), \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \\ \text{blank}(\text{CS}, \text{NOF}) &= \begin{cases} 2, & \text{CS} < 4 \text{ or } \text{NOF} < 4, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Refactoring approach: inline the class if it is used by a single client; otherwise extract the actually used functionality into a new class.

Abstract class

$$\text{Anx}_5 = \text{specGen}(\text{NOC}), \quad \text{specGen}(\text{NOC}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\text{NOC}}, & \text{NOC} > 0, \\ 2, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Refactoring approach: delete the class if it is unused; otherwise move necessary methods to subclasses.

Inappropriate intimacy

$$\text{Anx}_6 = 0.8 \cdot \frac{\text{CBO}}{\text{CBOR}} + 0.2 \cdot \frac{\text{RFC}}{\text{RFCR}}. \quad (11)$$

Refactoring approach: introduce getters and setters or relocate logic to the class that owns the data.

Middle Man The same formula as above applies.

Refactoring approach: merge the classes or move delegated logic back.

A.3 Structural Metrics

CS (Class Size) is the number of lines of code in a class, including comments and blank lines. NM (Number of Methods) is the total number of methods in the class. NOF (Number of Fields) is the number of static and non-static fields. CBO (Coupling Between Objects) measures how many classes interact with the given class through method or field usage. DIT (Depth of Inheritance Tree) is the path length from the hierarchy root to the class. WMC (Weighted Methods per Class) is the sum of method complexities, where complexity is estimated from conditionals, loops, and method calls.

A.4 Quality and Comparative Metrics

The change in average anxiety is computed as

$$\Delta Anx = \frac{1}{N} \sum (Anx_{i,before} - Anx_{i,after}),$$

where N is the number of classes and Anx_i is the average anxiety for class i . The ratios

$$Post_OK/All_Post \quad \text{and} \quad Tests_OK/All_Tests$$

measure formal correctness and functional preservation, respectively.

FP (False Positives) denotes changes that do not improve the code or may introduce new defects. FN (False Negatives) denotes problematic regions not detected or not corrected by the refactoring tool.

B Example UML* Fragment and OCL Constraints

Below are provided: (a) a program class before refactoring; (b) a fragment of UML* representation; and (c) examples of OCL invariants, preconditions, and postconditions.

B.1 Program Class Before Refactoring (C#)

```
namespace BadDesignApp.Services;

// Anx2: Divergent Change - changing logic requires editing many methods
// Anx6: Encapsulation violation - direct access to fields
// High coupling - classes tightly interact
public class OrderProcessor
{
```

```

// Public fields = encapsulation violation
public string OrderId;
public string UserId;
public OrderStatus Status;
public decimal Price;
public int ItemCount;

// Direct interaction with another class
private readonly PaymentProcessor _paymentProcessor;

public OrderProcessor()
{
    _paymentProcessor = new PaymentProcessor();
}

// Anæ2: Changing processing logic requires modifying many methods
public void Process(string orderId, string userId)
{
    OrderId = orderId;
    UserId = userId;
    Status = OrderStatus.Pending;

    // Directly changing another object's state
    _paymentProcessor.CurrentOrderId = orderId;
    _paymentProcessor.Amount = 0; // initialization

    ValidateOrder();
    CalculatePrice();
    ProcessPayment();
    UpdateStatus();
    NotifyUser();
}

// Anæ2: If validation changes, update this method and Process
private void ValidateOrder()
{
    if (string.IsNullOrEmpty(OrderId))
    {
        Status = OrderStatus.Invalid;
        _paymentProcessor.IsValid = false;
        return;
    }
    _paymentProcessor.IsValid = true;
}

// Anæ2: If pricing changes, update this method and Process
private void CalculatePrice()
{
    ItemCount = OrderId.Length; // intentionally poor logic for
    demonstration
}

```

```
        Price = itemCount * 10.5m;
        _paymentProcessor.Amount = Price;
    }

    // Anæ2: If payment changes, update this method and Process
    private void ProcessPayment()
    {
        if (_paymentProcessor.IsValid && _paymentProcessor.Amount > 0)
        {
            _paymentProcessor.Process();
            Status = OrderStatus.Paid;
        }
    }

    private void UpdateStatus()
    {
        if (Status == OrderStatus.Paid)
            Status = OrderStatus.Processing;
    }

    private void NotifyUser()
    {
        Console.WriteLine($"Order {OrderId} for user {UserId} is {Status}");
    }
}

public enum OrderStatus
{
    Pending,
    Invalid,
    Paid,
    Processing
}

// Tightly coupled class
public class PaymentProcessor
{
    public string CurrentOrderId;
    public decimal Amount;
    public bool IsValid;

    public void Process()
    {
        Console.WriteLine($"Processing payment {Amount:C} for order {CurrentOrderId}");
    }
}
```

B.2 Fragment of UML* Representation (Textual)

```

Classes and structural elements:

Class OrderProcessor
Attributes:
- OrderId : String
- UserId : String
- Status : OrderStatus
- Price : Decimal
- ItemCount : Integer
- _paymentProcessor : PaymentProcessor

Methods:
- Process(orderId : String, userId : String)
- ValidateOrder()
- CalculatePrice()
- ProcessPayment()
- UpdateStatus()
- NotifyUser()

Class PaymentProcessor
Attributes:
- CurrentOrderId : String
- Amount : Decimal
- IsValid : Boolean

Methods:
- Process()

Example of extended method description: OrderProcessor::Process()

ActionSequence AS_Process
|- locals:
|  '- LocalVariable tmpPrice : Decimal
|    '- scope -> AS_Process
'- actions:
  |- A1 : SingleTargetAction <<UpdateAction>>
  |- A2 : SingleTargetAction <<UpdateAction>>
  |- A3 : SingleTargetAction <<AccessAction>>
  '- A4 : SingleTargetAction <<UpdateAction>>

A1 = order initialization
A2 = set status Pending
A3 = access payment data
A4 = update status after payment

```

B.3 Examples of OCL Invariants, Preconditions, and Postconditions

```

Invariants

context SingleTargetAction
inv ValidTargetType:
    self.targetRefinement.ocIsKindOf(LocalVariable) or
    self.targetRefinement.ocIsKindOf(Parameter) or
    self.targetRefinement.ocIsKindOf(Attribute)

context SingleTargetAction
inv NoSubclassAttributeAccess:
    self.targetRefinement.ocIsKindOf(Attribute) implies
    self.targetRefinement.ocAsType(Attribute).owner =
    self.actionSequence.method.owner

context SingleTargetAction
inv LocalVariableScopeCorrect:
    self.targetRefinement.ocIsKindOf(LocalVariable) implies
    self.targetRefinement.ocAsType(LocalVariable).scope =
    self.actionSequence

Preconditions

context OrderProcessor::Process(orderId : String, userId : String)
pre OrderIdNotEmpty:
    not orderId.ocIsUndefined() and orderId <> ''

context OrderProcessor::ProcessPayment()
pre PaymentIsAllowed:
    self._paymentProcessor.IsValid = true and
    self._paymentProcessor.Amount > 0

Postconditions

context OrderProcessor::Process(orderId : String, userId : String)
post StatusUpdated:
    self.Status <> OrderStatus::Pending

context OrderProcessor::ProcessPayment()
post PaymentLeadsToStatusChange:
    self.Status = OrderStatus::Paid or
    self.Status = OrderStatus::Processing

```

C Engineering Details of UML* Extraction

C.1 Conventions and Scope

Section 3 of the main paper introduces the UML* extension itself: local variables, method actions, refined target/value links, and consistency constraints. This

appendix complements that description with engineering details: (1) the UML* extraction pipeline, (2) the algorithm for building *ActionSequence*, (3) rules for mapping C# constructs to UML* action types, (4) optional model enrichment via an LLM, and (5) export formats and reporting.

C.2 Architecture of the UML* Extraction Pipeline

UML* extraction is implemented as a modular pipeline:

- **CodeAnalyzer**: extracts UML* elements from C# source code and forms an initial set of relations.
- **HuggingFaceService**: performs optional LLM enrichment; when unavailable, deterministic fallback is used.
- **DeviationAnalyzer**: computes quality metrics and identifies deviations using anxiety functions.
- **UmlExporter**: exports the model and analysis results as JSON, PlantUML, and XMI-compatible XML, and generates report-oriented views.
- **DeviationReporter**: generates text or JSON reports linked to classes and metrics.

C.3 Extracting UML* from C# Code

The extraction process proceeds in five main steps:

1. prepare the project representation by scanning `.cs` files and building syntax trees together with a semantic model;
2. extract classes and interfaces, including names, namespaces, modifiers, base classes, and implemented interfaces;
3. analyze class members, including fields, properties, and method signatures;
4. analyze method bodies to build *ActionSequence*, extract local variables, assignments, calls, and member accesses, and avoid duplicate processing of AST nodes;
5. form inter-class relations such as inheritance and dependencies derived from actions, then normalize and deduplicate them.

C.4 Action Extraction Rules (AST \rightarrow Action)

The main mapping rules from C# syntax to UML* actions are:

- **InvocationExpression** \rightarrow **CallAction**: record the invoked method, its owner class if resolvable, and its arguments.
- **AssignmentExpression** \rightarrow **UpdateAction**: capture target refinement and value refinement.
- **MemberAccessExpression** \rightarrow **AccessAction**: record access to a field, property, or similar member together with its owner.

Composite expressions are analyzed recursively so that the resulting *ActionSequence* captures the observable behavior of the method as completely as possible.

C.5 Optional Model Enrichment Using an LLM

Two operation modes are supported:

- **LLM enrichment:** when an API token is available, a structured UML* description is sent to the service to refine actions, variables, and relations.
- **Deterministic fallback:** when the service is unavailable, rule-based enrichment is applied using already extracted entities.

This design improves robustness by treating the LLM as an optional enhancer rather than as the sole source of correctness.

C.6 Deviation Diagnostics and Export

After UML* construction, design-quality evaluation computes metrics and anxiety functions. The results are then exported in several formats:

- JSON for machine processing,
- PlantUML for diagram visualization,
- XMI-compatible XML for interoperability with UML tools.

Additional reports may include per-method views (locals and actions), per-class UML fragments, and deviation reports in text and/or JSON form.